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Institutional and Administrative Barriers to the Implementation of the National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA) Policy in Plateau State

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Abstract

Despite the establishment of the National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA) to promote equitable access to healthcare and financial protection for Nigerians, its effective implementation in Plateau State continues to face persistent institutional and administrative challenges such limited institutional capacity of the NHIA office, characterized by understaffing, insufficient logistics, and weak technical coordination. The study adopted Elite Theory of Public Policy propounded by Vilfredo Pareto in 1896. The population comprised 148 staff of the NHIA in Plateau State, from which a sample size of 107 was determined using Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) formula. Data were collected using

a structured questionnaire, and 91 valid responses were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25. Findings revealed that institutional and administrative barriers significantly influence the effective implementation of the NHIA in Plateau State. A large majority (82.5%) of respondents identified corruption and mismanagement of resources as key constraints. Similarly, weak monitoring and evaluation mechanisms (80.3%) were highlighted as major challenges, Furthermore, inadequate infrastructure (82.5%) and funding constraints (74.8%) were found to impede service delivery, corroborating. Political interference (86.8%) and legal gaps (75.8%) further weakened institutional effectiveness. Conversely, the study found relative strengths in administrative coordination between NHIA headquarters and the Plateau State office, leadership stability, staff competence, and digital record management. The study recommended stronger accountability systems, improved funding mechanisms, enhanced infrastructure, digitalized monitoring frameworks, and continuous capacity-building programs. Ensuring merit-based leadership appointments and enforcing regulatory compliance are also essential to achieving sustainable universal health coverage in Nigeria.

Keywords: Authority, Health, Implementation, Insurance and policy.

1. Introduction

The provision of affordable, accessible and quality healthcare service remains the thrust of the Universal Health Coverage. However, how these principles are being achieved under the National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA) is uncertain in Nigeria. The implementation of health insurance schemes has been widely recognized as a vital strategy for achieving Universal Health Coverage (UHC) and improving access to quality and affordable healthcare services (World Health Organization [WHO], 2021). Health insurance systems serve not only as financial risk-pooling mechanisms but also as institutional tools for promoting equity, efficiency, and sustainability in healthcare delivery (Kutzin, 2019; McIntyre et al., 2017). In many developed nations, strong

institutional and administrative frameworks are central to the efficient operation of health insurance programs. Countries such as Germany, Canada, and the United Kingdom have established well-coordinated administrative systems that emphasize accountability, transparency, and effective inter-agency collaboration in healthcare financing (Kutzin, 2019). According to scholars, these frameworks reduce fragmentation, enhance provider regulation, and minimize out-of-pocket expenditures for citizens, thereby ensuring equitable access to health services (Saltman, Busse, & Figueras, 2018). The success of such models demonstrates that robust institutional structures, effective governance, and policy coherence are critical prerequisites for sustainable health financing systems.

In Africa, several countries have introduced national health insurance schemes as part of broader health sector reforms aimed at expanding coverage and reducing financial barriers to healthcare access. However, the effectiveness of these schemes has often been undermined by institutional weaknesses, administrative inefficiencies, and chronic funding constraints (Agyepong & Abankwah, 2020; Okech & Lelegwe, 2016). For example, in Ghana, despite the establishment of the National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA), empirical studies reveal persistent challenges related to corruption, weak monitoring systems, and delays in claims reimbursement, which have adversely affected service delivery and the scheme's long-term sustainability (Agyepong & Abankwah, 2020). Similarly, Onyango (2021) observed that Kenya's National Hospital Insurance Fund (NHIF) has struggled with governance failures, poor accountability structures, and political interference, limiting its effectiveness in providing comprehensive health coverage.

In Nigeria, the National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS) was established in 1999 and officially renamed the National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA) in 2022 as a policy response to persistent inefficiencies in healthcare financing and access, with the objective of strengthening institutional capacity, improving service delivery, and expanding population coverage (Federal Government of Nigeria, 2022).

Ogundipe (2022) noted that the scheme was designed to address long-standing challenges such as fragmented healthcare financing, weak regulatory oversight, and excessive reliance on out-of-pocket payments. However, despite subsequent reforms and the recent restructuring of the NHIS, empirical studies indicated that implementation has continued to face serious institutional and administrative barriers. Afolabi and Oladipo (2023) argued that corruption, inadequate infrastructure, political interference, and weak monitoring and evaluation mechanisms have significantly undermined the effectiveness of the scheme. These challenges, according to Ogundipe (2022), have resulted in inefficiencies in service delivery, limited enrolment, and slow progress toward achieving universal health coverage in Nigeria.

At the sub-national level, particularly in Plateau State, the implementation of NHIS programs has been further constrained by limited funding, poor logistics support, weak inter-agency coordination, and regulatory inadequacies. Ishaku and Yakubu (2023) observed that inadequate monitoring and evaluation frameworks, frequent administrative changes, and bureaucratic delays have negatively affected policy continuity and program sustainability in the state. Additionally, limited technical capacity of administrative staff to manage complex health insurance processes has compounded implementation challenges. Consequently, the ability of the NHIA to achieve its stated objectives in Plateau State remains restricted by systemic institutional and administrative bottlenecks. Against this background, this study examines the institutional and administrative barriers to the implementation of the National Health Insurance Authority in Plateau State, Nigeria.

2. Statement of the Problem

The research problem is despite the establishment of the National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA) to promote equitable, affordable, and accessible healthcare services and to provide financial protection for Nigerians, its effective implementation in Plateau State continues to face persistent institutional and administrative challenges that undermine service quality. The NHIA was designed to address

inefficiencies in healthcare governance, expand population coverage, reduce out-of-pocket expenditure, and ensure accountability within the health system (Federal Ministry of Health, 2022). However, in Plateau State, these objectives have not been fully realized, as weaknesses in institutional structures, inadequate funding, and bureaucratic inefficiencies have significantly constrained the scheme's capacity to deliver affordable, accessible, and quality healthcare services to enrollees.

A major challenge peculiar to Plateau State is the limited institutional capacity of the NHIA office, which directly affects healthcare accessibility and service quality. The state office is often understaffed, poorly equipped, and constrained by insufficient technical and logistical resources, thereby limiting its ability to effectively coordinate stakeholders, monitor healthcare providers, and evaluate service delivery outcomes. These administrative shortcomings have resulted in delays in provider payments, weak supervision of healthcare facilities, and inconsistent enforcement of service standards, all of which negatively affect the affordability and quality of healthcare services available to beneficiaries. Aregbeshola and Khan (2018) argue that weak institutional frameworks within Nigeria's health insurance system significantly contribute to poor service delivery, low enrolment, and persistent financial barriers to healthcare access across states.

Empirical studies on health insurance implementation in Nigeria have largely focused on service delivery outcomes, enrolment levels, and system performance. For instance, Afolabi and Oladipo (2023) examined health insurance implementation and service delivery in Nigeria, while Zumunta, Yildam, and Igbochesi (2024) analyzed the role of communication in the success of health insurance schemes from the Plateau State Contributory Healthcare Management Agency perspective. Similarly, Pillah (2023) evaluated the performance and challenges of the NHIS at the national level, and Ambali, Salawu, and Shuaib (2025) assessed the relationship between health insurance and service quality in Nigeria. Ishaku and Yakubu (2023) also explored administrative efficiency and public health policy implementation in

Plateau State. However, despite these scholarly contributions, there remains a noticeable gap in the literature regarding a focused examination of the institutional and administrative barriers to the implementation of the National Health Insurance Authority in Plateau State, particularly as they affect the affordability, accessibility, and quality of healthcare services. This study intends to fill the gap.

3. Research Objective

The objective of this study is to examine the institutional and administrative barriers of the National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA) in Plateau State.

4. Conceptual Clarification

4.1 Institutional barriers

Institutional barriers are structural, organizational, and systemic factors within formal institutions that hinder the effective formulation, implementation, and monitoring of policies. These barriers often manifest as weak governance structures, inadequate human and technical resources, fragmented coordination among agencies, insufficient regulatory frameworks, and poorly defined roles and responsibilities (Aregbeshola & Khan, 2018; Peters, 2018; Hill & Hupe, 2014). According to North (1990), institutions encompass the formal rules, informal norms, and organizational structures that shape human interaction and policy outcomes, and weaknesses in these systems can impede efficiency, accountability, and equitable service delivery. In the context of health insurance, institutional barriers have been linked to low enrolment rates, limited coverage, and poor quality of services, as the capacity of implementing agencies to enforce policy, allocate resources effectively, and coordinate with healthcare providers is constrained (Afolabi & Oladipo, 2023; Ogundipe, 2022).

4.2 Administrative Barriers

Administrative barriers refer to challenges associated with bureaucratic processes, management practices, and operational inefficiencies that

impede policy implementation. These include delays in decision-making, cumbersome reporting procedures, inadequate monitoring and evaluation systems, political interference, and lack of accountability (Ogundipe, 2022; Ishaku & Yakubu, 2023; Hill & Hupe, 2014). Administrative barriers limit the capacity of public institutions to translate policies into intended outcomes by constraining timely resource allocation and enforcement of regulations (Peters, 2018).

4.3 National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA) Policy

The NHIA policy is Nigeria's legislative and operational framework for providing health insurance to achieve Universal Health Coverage (UHC). Originally established as the National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS) in 1999, it was renamed and strengthened by the NHIA Act of 2022 to expand coverage, ensure affordability, and improve regulatory oversight (Federal Government of Nigeria, 2022; WHO, 2021). The policy encompasses guidelines for enrollment, healthcare financing, provider accreditation, and benefit packages. Scholars emphasize that the effectiveness of NHIA policies depends on institutional strength, governance capacity, and administrative efficiency (Kutzin, 2019; McIntyre et al., 2017).

5. Theoretical Framework

Elite Theory of Public Policy was propounded by Vilfredo Pareto in 1896 and later advanced by Gaetano Mosca (1896) and Robert Michels (1911), with its application to public policy analysis further developed by C. Wright Mills (1956) and Thomas R. Dye (1966). The theory is anchored on the premise that power in society is concentrated in the hands of a small ruling elite who dominate political, economic, and administrative institutions, while the majority of the population remains largely excluded from meaningful participation in policy formulation and implementation. According to the theory, public policies are not primarily the outcome of popular demand but rather reflect the values, interests, and preferences of elites who control decision-making structures. The assumptions of Elite Theory emphasize that society is

divided into a governing elite and the masses, that elites control state institutions, and that public policies largely mirror elite interests. It assumes limited mass participation in governance, elite continuity through patronage and appointments, and incremental policy change that occurs mainly when there is consensus or competition among elites. These assumptions suggest that administrative inefficiencies, inequities, and policy failures persist not by accident but as outcomes of elite-dominated governance systems that prioritize political and personal interests over public welfare.

Elite Theory is relevant to the study because public policy implementation in developing societies where governance structures are centralized and bureaucratic processes are heavily politicized. Dye (2013) argued that elite dominance often leads to weak accountability, selective enforcement of regulations, and misallocation of public resources. In the health sector, elite control over financing, staffing, and regulatory oversight has been associated with unequal access to healthcare services, poor service quality, and persistent inefficiencies in health insurance schemes (Aregbeshola & Khan, 2018). Thus, the theory provides a useful framework for understanding why well-designed policies often fail at the implementation stage.

Elite Theory has attracted considerable scholarly criticism, particularly for its tendency to overemphasize elite dominance while underestimating the influence of civil society, professional associations, and institutional rules in shaping public policy outcomes. Dahl (1961) argued that modern democratic systems are characterized by multiple competing interest groups rather than a single, cohesive elite, suggesting that policy decisions often emerge from bargaining and negotiation among diverse actors. Similarly, Hill and Hupe (2014) contended that policy implementation is shaped not only by elite preferences but also by organizational routines, street-level bureaucrats, and institutional constraints, which Elite Theory does not adequately capture. Furthermore, critics argued that Elite Theory incorrectly assumes elite cohesion and uniformity of interests. According to Higley and Burton (2006), elites are frequently fragmented along ideological,

ethnic, and institutional lines, and such divisions can create opportunities for policy reform and accountability. This fragmentation challenges the deterministic view of elite control advanced by classical elite theorists and suggests that policy outcomes may reflect intra-elite competition rather than elite consensus alone. In addition, Elite Theory has limited predictive capacity because it focuses primarily on identifying who holds power rather than explaining how specific policies are implemented or transformed within bureaucratic and legal frameworks. Peters (2018) observed that public policy outcomes are often shaped by administrative procedures, legal mandates, and institutional norms that constrain elite discretion. As a result, Elite Theory provides a useful descriptive account of power concentration but offers limited insight into the complex operational dynamics of policy implementation, particularly in large and rule-bound public sector organizations.

Elite Theory is highly applicable to the study of institutional and administrative barriers to the implementation of the National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA) policy in Plateau State. Although the NHIA policy is designed to promote affordable, accessible, and quality healthcare services, its implementation is largely influenced by political and bureaucratic elites who control funding allocations, staffing decisions, provider accreditation, and regulatory enforcement. In Plateau State, elite-driven appointment processes often prioritize political loyalty over technical competence, resulting in weak institutional capacity, bureaucratic inefficiencies, and ineffective monitoring mechanisms. Budgetary decisions shaped by elite interests have also contributed to inadequate funding, delayed reimbursements, and infrastructural deficits in NHIA-accredited facilities. Consequently, Elite Theory provides a compelling analytical lens for understanding how elite dominance within political and administrative institutions constrains effective implementation of the NHIA policy and undermines the achievement of universal health coverage in Plateau State.

6. Empirical Review

Zumunta, Yildam and Igboechesi (2024) examined the communication strategies employed by the Plateau State Contributory Healthcare Management Agency and their impact on the citizens of Plateau State. A mixed-method research design was adopted, Findings revealed that PLASHEMA effectively applies corporate communication strategies, leading to a satisfactory level of public awareness about its activities. However, the overall outcomes of these communication processes were found to be moderate. The study recommended that the agency diversify its communication methods, extend its outreach using local languages, and engage professional information and public relations experts to enhance the effectiveness of its health insurance campaigns. The study left unresolved questions regarding the extent to which institutional and administrative barriers shape the effectiveness of health insurance schemes in Plateau State. This limitation reinforces the need for the present study, which goes beyond communication strategies to critically examine the institutional and administrative barriers affecting the implementation of the National Health Insurance Authority in Plateau State.

Ambali, Salawu and Shuaib (2025) analyzed health insurance and service quality in Nigeria's national health insurance policy. The study employed both primary and secondary data sources. Findings indicated significant disparities in health system performance across the states. Access to healthcare was highest Benue in (60.7%), Kwara (54.4%), and Nasarawa (58.1%), while Niger (24.7%) and Plateau (29.7%) lagged behind due to infrastructural and logistical deficiencies. Emergency responsiveness exhibited similar variations, with Nasarawa (51.8%), Kwara (49.4%), and Benue (41%) outperforming Niger (22.2%). The professionalism of healthcare providers also differed notably, as Nasarawa recorded the highest rating (77.4%) and Plateau the lowest (30.8%). The study recommended that improving service quality under the NHIS requires strategic collaboration between the National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA), state governments, and

regulatory agencies. It is also recommended increased investment in health infrastructure, continuous training of healthcare workers, establishment of community feedback systems, and enhancement of emergency response mechanisms. The study did not address how institutional and administrative barriers influence the implementation of the NHIA. This study seeks to assess the institutional and administrative constraints affecting the implementation of the National Health Insurance Authority in Plateau State.

7. Methodology

The population of this study was 148 drawn from the staff National Health insurance authority in Plateau State. The sample size was 107 derived through Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) formula. Out of the 107 copies of a questionnaire, ninety-one (91) were retrieved and analyzed, using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25. Data were analyzed, using a 5-point Likert scale with “1 = Strongly Disagreed, 2 = Disagreed, 3 = Undecided, 4 = Agreed, and 5 = Strongly Agreed”.

Thus:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & n = \frac{X^2 N P (1-P)}{e^2 (N-1) + X^2 P (1-P)} \\
 & n = \frac{3.841 \times 148 \times 0.5 \times 0.5}{((0.05)^2 \times 148 + (3.841 \times 0.5 \times 0.5))} \\
 & n = 142.117 \\
 & n = 142.117 \\
 & n = 107
 \end{aligned}$$

8. Results and Discussion

Table 8.1 Institutional and administrative barriers of the National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA) in Plateau

S/N	Statements	SD	D	U	A	SA	Total	Remark
1	Corruption and mismanagement of resources hinder the NHIA's ability to achieve its goals.	1 (1.1%)	8 (8.8%)	7 (7.7%)	45 (49.5%)	30 (33%)	91 (100%)	Agree
2	Weak monitoring and evaluation mechanisms hinder the effective implementation of NHIA policies in Plateau State.	6 (6.6%)	8 (8.8%)	4 (4.4%)	45 (49.5%)	28 (30.8%)	91 (91.1%)	Agree
3	The NHIA in Plateau State suffers from inadequate infrastructure and logistics support needed for effective service delivery.	1 (1.1%)	8 (8.8%)	7 (7.7%)	45 (49.5%)	30 (33%)	91 (100%)	Agree
4	The National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA) in Plateau State lacks adequate funding to implement its health programs effectively.	3 (3.3%)	12 (13.2%)	8 (8.8%)	39 (42.9%)	29 (31.9%)	91 (100%)	Agree
5	Political interference affects the NHIA's ability to execute its mandate independently.	2 (2.2%)	5 (5.5%)	5 (5.5%)	50 (54.9%)	29 (31.9%)	91 (100%)	Agree
6	Legal and regulatory gaps affect the NHIA's ability to enforce compliance with its policies.	7 (7.7%)	0	0	47 (51.6%)	22 (24.2%)	91 (100%)	Agree
7	There is insufficient coordination between the NHIA headquarters and the Plateau State office, leading to policy implementation	29 (31.9%)	41 (44.6%)	3 (3.3%)	12 (13.2%)	7 (7.6%)	91 (100%)	Disagree
8	Frequent changes in administrative leadership negatively affect policy continuity in the NHIA system.	23 (25.3%)	59 (64.9%)	1 (1.1%)	15 (16.5%)	3 (3.3%)	91 (100%)	Disagree
9	The staff of the NHIA in Plateau State are not adequately trained to implement and manage health insurance programs efficiently.	26 (28.6%)	44 (47.8%)	4 (4.4%)	9 (9.9%)	8 (8.8%)	91 (100%)	Disagree
10	Poor record-keeping and data management systems limit the effectiveness of NHIA operations in Plateau State.	23 (25.3%)	38 (41.8%)	2 (2.2%)	18 (19.8%)	10 (11%)	91 (100%)	Disagree

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2025

The table reveals that the majority (82.5%) agreed that corruption and mismanagement of resources hinder the NHIA's ability to achieve its goals, indicating that unethical practices and poor accountability remain significant barriers to effective policy implementation. Similarly, about 80.3% of respondents agreed that weak monitoring and evaluation mechanisms adversely affect the execution of NHIA policies in the state, suggesting that the absence of robust oversight structures reduces program efficiency. Furthermore, 82.5% affirmed that inadequate infrastructure and logistics support impede effective service delivery, highlighting a critical operational challenge within the NHIA system. In addition, 74.8% of respondents agreed that funding constraints negatively impact the implementation of NHIA health programs, while 86.8% identified political interference as a major impediment to the agency's ability to operate independently. Also, 75.8% agreed that legal

and regulatory gaps weaken NHIA's enforcement capacity, indicating the need for stronger institutional frameworks and clearer policy guidelines.

On the other hand, 76.1% of respondents disagreed that there is insufficient coordination between the NHIA headquarters and the Plateau State office, implying that administrative alignment and communication may not be major issues. Similarly, 79.2% disagreed that frequent leadership changes affect policy continuity, suggesting that administrative turnover has not significantly disrupted operations. In addition, 77% of respondents disagreed that NHIA staff are inadequately trained, indicating that personnel possess adequate knowledge and skills for program implementation. Lastly, 67.1% disagreed that poor record-keeping and data management limit NHIA effectiveness, showing that data handling systems are relatively functional.

9. Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study reveal that institutional and administrative barriers significantly influence the effective implementation of the National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA) in Plateau State. A large majority (82.5%) of respondents agreed that corruption and mismanagement of resources hinder the NHIA's ability to achieve its goals. This finding confirms the position of Adebayo and Yusuf (2022), who observed that corruption within public health institutions diverts essential funds from service delivery, thereby undermining policy outcomes and eroding public confidence. Ogunleye (2020) also emphasized that when accountability systems are weak, resources meant for healthcare infrastructure and personnel welfare are often misappropriated, resulting in inefficiency and inequitable access to care.

Equally, weak monitoring and evaluation mechanisms were cited by 80.3% of respondents as a major challenge to NHIA policy execution in Plateau State. This agrees with Eze and Okonkwo (2020), who stressed that ineffective monitoring and evaluation (M&E) structures limit feedback, data accuracy, and accountability in health program

implementation. Similarly, Brals et al. (2017) found that the absence of systematic M&E prevents early detection of inefficiencies, thereby delaying policy reform and improvement. Another important barrier identified by 82.5% of respondents was the lack of adequate infrastructure and logistics support, which affects the smooth delivery of NHIA services. This corroborates the findings of Afolayan and Muhammed (2011), who argued that infrastructural inadequacy particularly in rural and hard-to-reach areas limits access to essential health services. Brals et al. (2017) similarly noted that the success of national health insurance programs depends heavily on the availability of health facilities, trained personnel, and logistics such as transportation and ICT systems. The implication is that infrastructure and logistics deficits hinder both accessibility and quality of care, making it difficult for the NHIA to achieve its universal coverage goals in Plateau State.

Funding constraints were also identified by 74.8% of respondents as a critical challenge facing the NHIA in Plateau State. This finding resonates with Adeleke (2021), who highlighted that inadequate funding remains one of the most persistent bottlenecks to effective health insurance implementation in Nigeria. Insufficient budgetary allocation to the health sector weakens service delivery, delays claims settlement, and restricts the expansion of insurance coverage. In a similar view, Ojo and Ibrahim (2022) contended that sustainable health insurance requires diversified funding sources and timely disbursement mechanisms to ensure continuity in service delivery.

Political interference emerged as the most pronounced constraint, as 86.8% of respondents agreed that political influence disrupts NHIA's independent functioning. This aligns with the observations of Olalekan (2019) and Okeke (2023), who reported that undue political involvement in administrative processes distorts merit-based decisions, leading to inefficiencies and loss of institutional credibility. Moreover, 75.8% of respondents agreed that legal and regulatory gaps affect the NHIA's enforcement capacity. This supports Adeyemi (2021) and World Health Organization (2022) reports that weak institutional laws

and poor enforcement frameworks reduce compliance among stakeholders and create loopholes for administrative abuse.

Conversely, 76.1% of respondents disagreed that there is insufficient coordination between the NHIA headquarters and its Plateau State office, indicating a relatively effective administrative relationship. This finding contrasts with Usman (2020), who reported coordination challenges between federal and state-level agencies in other regions. The result suggests that in Plateau State, communication, policy alignment, and administrative synergy may be functioning adequately. Likewise, 79.2% of respondents disagreed that frequent leadership changes disrupt policy continuity, suggesting a measure of stability in NHIA management in the state. This stability is essential for sustaining institutional memory and long-term policy implementation.

Additionally, 77% of respondents disagreed that NHIA staff are inadequately trained, implying that the organization has invested in staff development and capacity-building programs. This finding aligns with Nwosu and Adebajo (2021), who emphasized that staff training enhances technical competence and commitment in public service delivery. Similarly, 67.1% of respondents disagreed that poor record-keeping limits NHIA effectiveness, which indicates that Plateau State has made progress in data management and digital record systems. This contrasts with earlier findings by Olowookere et al. (2018), who identified poor documentation as a critical issue in health administration across Nigeria.

10. Conclusion

The study examined the institutional and administrative barriers affecting the effective implementation of the National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA) in Plateau State. The findings revealed that while the NHIA plays a crucial role in promoting equitable access to healthcare services, several systemic and administrative challenges continue to undermine its performance. The major barriers identified include corruption and mismanagement of resources, weak monitoring and evaluation mechanisms, inadequate infrastructure and logistics,

insufficient funding, political interference, and legal or regulatory deficiencies.

11. Recommendations

The Federal Government of Nigeria, in collaboration with the NHIA Governing Board, should prioritize the eradication of corruption and ensure strict accountability mechanisms through regular audits, transparent budgeting, and the enforcement of sanctions against unethical practices. This will enhance public trust and ensure that resources are effectively utilized for the intended purposes. Secondly, the Federal Ministry of Health (FMoH) and NHIA monitoring units should establish a comprehensive monitoring and evaluation framework that integrates digital reporting tools and periodic performance assessments to track the progress of policy implementation and service delivery. The NHIA State Office should collaborate with the Plateau State Ministry of Health to address infrastructural and logistical deficiencies by ensuring that health facilities are adequately equipped and that transport systems for medical outreach are improved. Adequate funding remains a crucial determinant of program success; hence, the National Assembly should ensure timely budgetary allocations and release of funds to the NHIA to facilitate uninterrupted health service delivery. Additionally, donor agencies and development partners such as the World Health Organization (WHO) and the World Bank should be encouraged to provide technical and financial support to strengthen the scheme's sustainability.

The Presidency and Federal Civil Service Commission should ensure that appointments within NHIA are based strictly on merit and professional competence rather than political affiliations. Also, the National Assembly should review and amend existing legal frameworks governing the NHIA to close regulatory gaps and empower the agency with stronger enforcement authority. The NHIA Training and Human Resource Department should continue to provide continuous capacity-building programs to enhance staff competencies, while the Information and Communications Technology (ICT) Department should further

strengthen data management systems to ensure evidence-based decision-making and improved service delivery.

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